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MENIE JUMAWAN DAGALA, MAED- ELT
Assistant Professor III
Siquijor State College
mjdagala@siquijorstate.edu.ph

“TO THE ENCHANTED SHORE OF SIQUIJOR ISLAND”

Oh, glistening and glowing sea and san,
Your pebbles shine like gold, warm as His laughter.
The bluest sky kisses you softly,
And Siquijodnons live and dream with you with longing.

The whispering waves tell of a secret.
Your tides bring every dream in the golden foam,
To the farthest ocean and its fate,
and every breathtaking sunset echoes home
and warmth and the desire to live a good life.

Oh Siquijor, your sea breeze feels a mother's embrace.
The stories of folks who whirl around with solace.
In your salty kiss, I found peace.
In your wonder, I found healing and grace.
When the world grew heavy and unyielding,
Each ripple soothes our weariness and burdens.

Your silvery and silky water
are potions that hold the heart of every woman
and pushes every man to confess their feelings.
Even the wanderers are captivated and lured
Not to leave again and wish to be cradled.

But now, I am pained to see you bruised,
Careless hands that cast gray shadows on your glow.
The noise drowns your sacred hush,
The battles of every man darken your sanctuary.
Yet, you endure -

Oh Siquijor shore, the healer of weary souls,
You bring magic and your shores' timeless hymns,
Brings so much nostalgia of friendship and time.

An extension of God's hand and devotion
Our love potion and a keeper of eternal stories,
May those who walk your shores learn to love you
As you loved us all.